

Antifertility Screening and Phytochemical Investigation of *Ruellia prostrata* poir

C. K. ANDHIWAL*, CHANDRA HAS
and

R. P. VARSHNEY

Research Laboratories, Chemistry Department, S. V. College,
Aligarh-202 001

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RUPELLIA prostrata poir (family : Acanthaceae) is a wild herbaceous plant. The juice of the leaves, boiled with little salt, is supposed to correct a depraved state of the humors on Malabar coast. It is also given with liquid copal as a remedy for gonorrhoea. The root of *R. suffruticosa* are given to cause abortion¹. Considering the medicinal importance of *Ruellia* species, the phytochemical investigation and antifertility screening of the plant were undertaken and the results reported in this note.

Experimental

The plant material (1.1 kg) was dried in shade, ground and extracted with boiling petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) for 24 h. After usual work up, the dark green neutral extract (6.2 g) was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (30-fold excess) which gave the following fractions :

Fraction A : Column on elution with petroleum ether and trituration from acetone yielded a white amorphous product (150 mg), m.p. 73–74° and homogeneous on tlc (CHCl₃ ; R_f, 0.92). Ir spectrum of this product indicated it to be a longchain aliphatic ester showing prominent peaks at 1715 and 1725 cm⁻¹. This fraction was then analysed by glc (alone and with added C₁₈-ester to serve as a standard for chainlength). It represented according to glc analysis, the homologous series of long-chain esters (C₄₂–C₆₀) with a maximum of C₅₄-ester (20.8%). Even-numbered members prevailed as usual^{2,3}. However, odd-numbered esters were also found in small quantities. The actual composition of fatty acids and alcohols in natural esters was not determined, but according to the results published^{4,5} earlier, it was supposed that single chromatographic peaks do not represent individual substances but mixtures of esters.

Fraction B : Further elution of the column with petroleum ether–benzene (3 : 1, v/v) gave lupeol, which upon crystallisation from methanol yielded shining crystals (75 mg), m.p. 211–12°. It was acetylated in Ac₂O–pyridine and the acetate was identified as lupeol acetate by glc (RRt, 1.93 ; OV-17 SCOT glass capillary column) and mass fragmentation pattern.

Fraction C : The next fraction on elution with petroleum ether–benzene (1 : 3, v/v) was composed of sterols, m.p. 126–28°. The fraction was acetylated in Ac₂O–pyridine. The glc analysis of this total acetylated sterol fraction indicated it to be a mixture of sitosterol, stigmasterol and campesterol.

Antifertility screening : The petroleum ether, ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *R. prostrata* poir were also screened for their possible antifertility effect on female albino rats by a method standardised by Khanna and Chaudhury⁶. In the present study, 40% activity was observed in the aqueous extract at a dose of 500 mg/kg and 20% in the petroleum ether and aqueous extracts at a dose of 100 mg/kg body weight ; while ethanolic extract was totally inactive.

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Free Amino Acids of *Argemone mexicana*

B. DINDA* and (MRS.) J. BANDYOPADHYAY

Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University Post Graduate Centre, Agartala-799 004

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Argemone mexicana Linn.¹ (Papaveraceae) is an annual herb with prickly leaves, bright yellow flowers and bristly capsules containing many seeds resembling black mustard seeds. It is an American plant which has run wild throughout India. The seed-oil and fresh yellow milky juice of the plant are used externally for the treatment^{1,2} of dropsy, jaundice, scabies, syphilitic ulcers, ophthalmia, respiratory disorders and constipation. Previous investigators reported the presence of a number of isoquinoline alkaloids²⁻¹⁰, flavonoids¹⁰⁻¹⁹, phenolics²⁰, sugars¹⁰ and fatty acids²¹⁻²³ in the plant,

* Present address : 1/64 Ice Factory Road, Surender Nagar, Aligarh.